

Analysis of Difficulties of PPL FKIP UIR Students in Implementing the Independent Curriculum

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Abstract:-

Introduction: This study generally aims to analyze the difficulties of UIR FKIP students when carrying out PPL in Pekanbaru in implementing the independent curriculum.

Method: This type of research is quantitative with an analytic descriptive design on 114 PPL students of the UIR Pekanbaru Riau FKIP who have implemented the independent curriculum. This research data is in the form of secondary data from questionnaires. The Results of the study concluded (a) UIR FKIP students had difficulty in two indicators, namely learning administration planning and planning and implementation of assessments. (b) UIR FKIP students found it easy to carry out independent curriculum learning during PPL.

Discussion: The curriculum is an important instrument that contributes to creating inclusive learning. Inclusiveness is not only about accepting students with special needs. However, inclusive means that the education unit is able to organize a learning climate that accepts and respects differences, both social, cultural, religious and ethnic differences. Learning that accepts the physical, religious and identity of the students.

Keywords:- Difficulty; PPL students; Freedom Curriculum.

I. INTRODUCTION

Curriculum changes are demands of developments in knowledge and technology that must be carried out. Especially considering that the 2013 curriculum has been running for several years, and teachers have been able to adapt or get used to this curriculum. The 2013 curriculum is a good curriculum to be applied in the learning process. So, why should the 2013 Curriculum be replaced with the Independent Curriculum?

In the Independent Curriculum, 20-30% of lesson hours from each subject are allocated for the Pancasila Student Profile Strengthening Project (P5). Through learning based on the Strengthening Pancasila Student Profile Project (P5) in the independent curriculum, students are given the opportunity to hone self-confidence, build cooperation and tolerance in developing creativity to create innovative work.

Law of the Republic of Indonesia Number 14 of 2005 concerning Teachers and Lecturers (UU No. 14/2005 concerning Teachers and Lecturers) mandates that teachers and lecturers are a profession. According to this law, "profession" is defined as a special job that is paid according to its skills or

duties (1). The implication is that teachers can only be held by people who are professionals in their field. One of the characteristics of a professional is that he must be able to carry out his responsibilities as an educator, including understanding and implementing the applicable curriculum, including the independent curriculum. This research is related to the existence of dualism in the implementation of the education curriculum in junior high schools (SMP) and senior high schools (SMA), where at the time this research was conducted there were still many PPL students who experienced obstacles in implementing the Independent Curriculum.

Preliminary information obtained by the author through interviews indicates that the reasons for not being ready to implement the Independent Curriculum include the following: (i) there has been no socialization regarding the procedures for its development in planning teaching programs, especially the content; (ii) PPL students' lack of understanding in developing curriculum content into more detailed objectives, namely learning indicators; (iii) difficulty in finding material that matches the indicators and curriculum content as well as needs analysis (AK), both national needs, institutions, students and the community using graduates; (iv) difficulties in preparing teaching materials and evaluating them; (2).

The aspects mentioned above are the main problems that really require immediate resolution, bearing in mind that all secondary schools have been recommended to implement the independent curriculum since 2020. In fact, in principle there is no significant difference between the content of the Independent Curriculum and the previous curriculum, namely Curriculum 13 (K13). One of the differences between the two is that K-13, which is also allocated 3-4 hours/week (for middle and high school) is more integrative, developing discourse that contains moral values, such as: honesty, discipline, independence, gathering/collaboration, caring, responsibility, self-confidence, critical/creative and respect.

In connection with the existence of the implementation of the Independent Curriculum, the results of initial observations of this research indicate that there are still many PPL students who have not been able to develop teaching materials that contain the moral values mentioned above, especially when related to the presentation of discourse which must be presented through the development of integrated skills (integrated skills).), for example listening and speaking, reading and writing, or even integrated for the four language skills. Apart from the problems mentioned above, teachers as members of the regional community should also actively participate in improving the region where they work.

II. METHOD

In this study, researchers used a type of descriptive quantitative research. The research was carried out in August 2023. This research was carried out at the Faculty of Teacher Training and Education, Riau Islamic University in 2023. The population is all subjects, variables, concepts or phenomena that will be studied (Morissan, 2012). The population in this study were all final year students at the University's Faculty of

Teacher Training and Education. Meanwhile the sample was calculated based on a percentage, namely 20% (120).

III. ANALYSIS

After the data description above, data analysis was then carried out. From the four indicators studied, it can be seen that what is difficult for students in implementing the independent curriculum is in preparing and compiling assessments. For more details, see the table

Table 1: Distribution of indicator data

	Very Difficult		Difficult		Easy		So Easy		Total	Category	
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%			
Teaching administration preparation	21	3,69	265	46,50	263	46,13	21	3,69	570	65,17	Difficult
Preparation for teaching implementation	13	2,85	198	43,42	226	49,56	19	4,16	456	60,6	Easy
Implementation of learning	19	2,77	258	37,72	381	55,70	26	3,80	684	59,8	Easy
Carrying out assessments	17	3,72	233	51,09	200	43,86	6	1,32	456	64,3	Difficult

A. Descriptive calculation of Teaching Preparation Administration

$$\frac{(21 \times 4) + (265 \times 3) + (263 \times 2) + (21 \times 1)}{570 \times 4} \times 100\% =$$

$$\frac{84 + 795 + 586 + 21}{2280} \times 100\% =$$

$$\frac{1486}{2280} \times 100\% = 65,17\%$$

From administrative calculations, teaching preparation is in the "difficult" category with a score of 65.17%. This means that the administration of teaching preparation is in the range of 62.50% – 81.24%, this percentage is in accordance with the criteria by Riduwan (2009)

B. Calculation of the description of Preparation for Implementation of Learning

$$\frac{(13 \times 4) + (198 \times 3) + (226 \times 2) + (19 \times 1)}{456 \times 4} \times 100\% =$$

$$\frac{42 + 594 + 452 + 19}{1824} \times 100\% =$$

$$\frac{1107}{1824} \times 100\% = 60,60\%$$

From the calculation of the Preparation for the Implementation of Learning, it is in the "easy" category which has a score of 60.60%. This means that the administration of teaching preparation is in the range of 43.75 – 62.40%, this percentage is in accordance with the criteria by Riduwan (2009)

C. Calculation of descriptions of teaching implementation

$$\frac{(19 \times 4) + (258 \times 3) + (381 \times 2) + (26 \times 1)}{684 \times 4} \times 100\% =$$

$$\frac{76 + 774 + 762 + 26}{2736} \times 100\% =$$

$$\frac{1638}{2736} \times 100\% = 59,82\%$$

From the calculations, the Implementation of Learning is in the "easy" category with a score of 59.82%. This means that the administration of teaching preparation is in the range of 43.75 – 62.40%, this percentage is in accordance with the criteria by Riduwan (2009)

D. Calculation of the Description of the Implementation of the Assessment

$$\frac{(17 \times 4) + (233 \times 3) + (200 \times 2) + (6 \times 1)}{456 \times 4} \times 100\% =$$

$$\frac{68 + 699 + 400 + 6}{1824} \times 100\% =$$

$$\frac{1173}{1824} \times 100\% = 64,30\%$$

From the calculations, the implementation of the chest assessment in the "difficult" category achieved a score of 64.30%. This means that the administration of teaching preparation is in the range of 62.50% – 81.24%, this percentage is in accordance with the criteria by Riduwan (2009)

IV. DISCUSSION

From the results of the data analysis above, it can be seen that from the four indicators seen regarding student knowledge and the implementation of the Medeka curriculum by UIR FKIP students when carrying out field practice or PPL it turns out that students have more difficulty with learning administration. As we know that in this curriculum, learning content is designed to be more optimal, providing sufficient time for students to understand concepts and develop competencies. Teachers also have the freedom to choose a variety of learning tools, so that learning can be adapted to the learning needs and interests of students. The project which aims to strengthen the attainment of the Pancasila student profile is developed with a theme-based approach set by the government. This project is not intended to achieve certain learning achievement targets, so it is not tied to certain subject content. In general,

in implementing and compiling tools in the independent curriculum there are several components.

Curriculum changes in Indonesia are one of the major changes in the world of education. Currently, the independent learning curriculum has become an option in the world of education, because the Ministry of Education and Culture needs to socialize it first so that this independent curriculum can become a curriculum. So this independent learning curriculum is not required to be implemented in all schools. The Ministry of Education and Culture explained that there are no specific criteria for educational units that wish to apply this curriculum, unlike the 2013 curriculum which prioritized schools that have accreditation A. The Ministry of Education and Culture is making efforts to change this curriculum to overcome existing problems.

This independent learning curriculum focuses on character development, student competence, and honing children's interests and talents as early as possible. This further reduces the amount of material given and assignments that require students to memorize. Meanwhile, the 2013 curriculum focuses on increasing and balancing attitudes, skills, and knowledge competencies. Apart from that, the 2013 curriculum focuses on the majors chosen by students. From this, it turns out that there are still many people who reject this curriculum change. This curriculum change was considered very sudden

The large demands of the independent curriculum make it difficult for students to prepare learning plans and assessment plans. However, in the implementation in the classroom students do not experience difficulties. The independent curriculum focuses on character development, student competence, and honing children's interests and talents. From this change in the independent curriculum, many students rejected the existence of this curriculum, because this change was considered very sudden. Even though the subjects to be taught are made simpler, the level of knowledge and understanding that students have will decrease because the subjects are not studied in their entirety. So that students who use this independent curriculum are not left behind in learning material, teachers should not be relaxed in delivering learning material.

Thus, the curriculum between schools can and should be different, according to the characteristics of students and school conditions, while still referring to the same curriculum framework. Changes in the curriculum framework certainly demand adaptation by all elements of the education system. This process requires careful management so that it produces the impact we want, namely improving the quality of learning and education in Indonesia. Therefore, the Ministry of Education and Culture provides curriculum options as one of the change management efforts.

National curriculum changes will only occur in 2024. At that time, the Independent Curriculum has gone through 3 years of improvement iterations in various schools/madrasahs and regions. In 2024 there will be quite a number of schools/madrasahs in each region that have studied the Independent Curriculum and can later become learning partners for other schools/madrasahs. This phased approach gives teachers, principals and the education office time to learn. The learning process of these key actors is important because this learning process forms the foundation of the educational transformation that we aspire to. Let's remember, the goal of curriculum change is to overcome a learning crisis. We want to make schools a safe, inclusive and fun place to learn.

For this reason, the Ministry of Education and Culture is making systemic changes, not just the curriculum. We are reforming the education evaluation system, organizing the teacher recruitment and training system, aligning vocational education with the world of work, assisting education offices, and strengthening budgets and institutions. Such systemic changes certainly cannot happen in an instant. It is hoped that step by step changes in the curriculum will provide adequate time for all key elements so that the foundation for transforming our education can be firmly and firmly planted.

There is one criterion, namely being interested in implementing the Independent Curriculum to improve learning. Principals of schools/madrasahs who wish to implement the Independent Curriculum will be asked to study material prepared by the Ministry of Education and Culture on the concept of the Independent Curriculum. Furthermore, if after studying the material the school decides to give it a try, they will be asked to complete an application form and a short survey. So, the process is registration and data collection, not selection. The Ministry of Education and Culture believes that the willingness of school/madrasah principals and teachers to understand and adapt the curriculum in their respective contexts is the key to success. Thus, the Merdeka Curriculum can be implemented in all schools/madrasahs, not limited to schools that have good facilities and in urban areas. However, we realize that the level of readiness of schools/madrasahs varies due to gaps in the quality of schools/madrasahs.

Therefore, the Ministry of Education and Culture has prepared a curriculum implementation level scheme, based on the results of a survey filled out by schools when registering. Once again, there is no selection in this registration process. The Ministry of Education and Culture will later map the level of readiness and prepare assistance according to needs. The curriculum is an important instrument that contributes to creating inclusive learning. Inclusiveness is not only about accepting students with special needs. However, inclusive means that the education unit is able to organize a learning climate that accepts and respects differences, both social, cultural, religious and ethnic differences. Learning that accepts the physical, religious and identity of the students.

V. CONCLUSION

Referring to the research objectives and based on the description above, it can be concluded: (a) FKIP UIR students have difficulty in two indicators, namely planning learning administration and planning and implementing assessments, (b) FKIP UIR students find it easy to carry out independent curriculum learning during PPL.

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